

**ORGANIZING MODERN STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT ACTIVITY IN
SMALL BUSINESS SUBJECTS**

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On the basis of ensuring socio-economic stability in Uzbekistan from year to year, increasing the welfare of the population, the level of consumption, employment and income, filling the domestic consumer market with local goods, and ensuring the competitiveness of our national goods in foreign markets, small business entities it should be noted that it has a special place.

From the first days of our independence, great attention was paid to ownership relations. As a result of the reforms carried out gradually over the years, today small business is becoming the backbone of our country's economy. In order to achieve these results, the state support of small business entities, ensuring economic freedom, creating legal bases for operation, financial is being achieved due to the strengthening of economic support. Small business and private entrepreneurship are defined as the priority direction of our country's economy. Over the past 5 years, about 2,000 laws, decrees and decisions aimed at the development of this industry have been adopted. On August 20, 2021, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev held an open dialogue with entrepreneurs. In it, a number of innovations were announced in the directions of granting loans only in soums, news for micro-finance organizations, reducing the tax burden for business, land sale and privatization, creating infrastructure, supporting exporters, developing the transport-logistics system, and simplifying business procedures. Now, in a word, small business entities are fully supported by the state.

Only the issue of entrepreneurs' ability to run their own business remains.

In particular, our local entrepreneurs face problems such as studying the market, offering goods and services that meet the needs of consumers, working in the fight against competition, strengthening their position in the market, that is, establishing a marketing service.

Based on this, this article describes the problems of organizing marketing services in the activities of small business entities and their solutions. It is known from the experience of world practice that the main problems of small business entities are related to finance, management and marketing. If we pay attention to the analysis of foreign sources, we will see a clear proof of this. Here are the top 10 business issues most important to small businesses: financial management, building a quality team, providing employee health care, building brand identity, scaling your business, complying with regulations, managing cash flow, effective leadership you need to be, manage time, know when to delegate. Nicky La Marco, a renowned small business expert, has been researching small business issues for many years. Being a small business owner isn't easy, according to Nikki LaMarco. Small businesses have to deal with challenges at different levels, from local to international. These challenges force any small business entity to upgrade to the level of a business owner or give up altogether. At the same time, it helps to know what challenges to expect so that the business owner is ready to overcome them when the time comes.

In accordance with marketing principles, all aspects of the economic activity of modern small enterprises should be planned and implemented taking into account market requirements and consumer needs. In Uzbekistan, it would be appropriate for small business entities to plan their production and sales activities, taking into account market requirements and consumer needs. It should be said that the great achievements of modern small enterprises in the field of production and sales, the variety and quality of their manufactured goods, their penetration into foreign markets, the creation of optimal production according to the scale of

foreign trade operations, all these are the result of the use of marketing.

Jay Conrad Levinson, another famous American advertising expert dealing with small business problems and their solutions, wrote in 1984 that small businesses cannot afford expensive advertising. They mention the use of "partisan marketing (guerrilla marketing)" in such conditions. Guerrilla marketing is a low-budget advertising and marketing method.

Kotler F., a leading marketing scientist, has also conducted extensive research on the issue of organizing marketing services in small enterprises. According to Kotler F., marketing service in small enterprises depends on the entrepreneur's own preparation, that is, marketing skills and abilities. Or, a marketing service can be set up by other well-trained, knowledgeable and skilled economic specialists.

In addition, Ismail Ruiz, a research scientist with famous small business problems, noted the following problems facing small business entities during his research: cyber security problems, problems related to tax legislation, developing health insurance market, uncertainty about the economy, sun Artificial intelligence, emerging social media, and a growing need for mobile-friendly websites.

According to Ismail Ruiz, most small businesses do not have a marketing department. Marketing issues are considered as part of the general work of a small business entity.

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